

**STUDIES ON THE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PARAMETERES AND
MACRO-INVERTEBRATE COMMUNITY OF THREE SELECTED
FRESH WATER PONDS OF AURANGABAD, BIHAR**

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ABSTRACT

The present study deals with three fresh water ponds of district Aurangabad, Bihar, during the period of one year from Dec 2015 to Nov 2016 and was designed to assess the quality of pond water, pond sediments, relative abundance and richness of macro-invertebrate species inhabiting the selected ponds. The three ponds of known historic interest namely Pond I (Umga), Pond II (Ranipokharadeo) & Pond III (Patalganga) have cultural and religious value. The study of the selected ponds was conducted with respect to the Physico-chemical parameters of pond water including Temperature, pH, Total alkalinity, Free CO₂, Dissolved oxygen, Electrical conductivity, Transparency, and Biological oxygen demand as well as Physico-chemical parameters of pond bottom sediments including pH, Organic carbon, Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium to observe the nutrient status of ponds.. The results of the Physico-chemical parameters studied in various months were evaluated and compared for all the three fresh water ponds to quantify overall pond water quality status of the area to see their impact on macro-invertebrate survival and growth as well as other possibilities of utilizing the pond area as aquaculture. The attributes of macro-invertebrate, showing sensitivity to environmental changes makes them attractive biological indicators in biological assessment programs and hence acts as key indicators of water quality condition. Hence by measuring the number of different species of macro- invertebrate (Richness) and total number of macro- invertebrates (Abundance) in a pond, we can assess the health of the water ecosystem. Thus the relative abundance and richness of macro-invertebrate species inhabiting the selected ponds were also recorded.

Keywords: Physico-chemical parameters, Macro-invertebrate, Fresh water ponds,

INTRODUCTION

Water is the main source of energy and governs the evolution on the earth. It is probably the only natural resource to touch all aspects of human civilization from agricultural and industrial development to cultural and religious values rooted in society. All living organisms on the earth are dependent on water for their survival as it is required as a medium for various physiological processes. Majority of water available on earth is saline in nature; only a small quantity exists as fresh water. Well, 97.5 % is sea water unfit for human consumption. Less than 1% of fresh water is present in ponds, lakes, rivers, dams, etc., which is used by man for consumption and other purposes. Freshwater is the life blood of our planet and may be regarded as “pillar of our civilization”. Recent evidence suggests that fresh water systems are more imperiled than marine

and terrestrial ones (Sala, 2000, Dudgeon, 2006). Fresh water has become a scarce commodity due to over exploitation and pollution (Ghose & Basu, 1968; Gupta & Shukla, 2006; Patil & Tijare, 2001; Singh & Mathur, 2005). According to an estimate about 70% of all the available water in our country is polluted due to the discharge of effluents from the industries, domestic waste, land and agricultural drainage (Shrivastava & Kanungo, 2013). Chemicals are a major source of water contamination that is introduced during water movement through geological materials (Kataria, Gupta, Kushwaha, Kashyap, Trivedi, Bhadoriya, & Bandewar, 2011). Fertilizers and pesticides are major contributors to water pollution. Weathering of rocks, leaching of soils and mining processing, etc., these are contaminating natural water (Manjare, Vhanalakar, & Muley, 2010).

Water quality refers to the chemical, physical, biological and radiological characteristics of water (Diersing & Nancy, 2009). It is a measure of the condition of water relative to the requirements of one or more biotic species and or to any human need or purpose (Johnson, Ambrose, Bassett, Bowen, Crummey, Isaacson, Johnson, Lamb, Saul, & Winter-Nelson, 1997). The quality of a water of pond refers to all the components of water which supports both the survival and optimum growth of aquatic organism. Water quality conditions are controlled by both natural processes and human influences. Natural factors such as source of pond water and the nature of soil and rocks in the pond watershed influence the pond water characteristics. Water quality is important in pond because water quality imbalances can cause stress, poor growth, and mortality of culture species (Boyd & Tucker, 1998). Water quality is strongly influenced by feed inputs, and ponds with high feeding rates frequently have more severe problems with low dissolved oxygen concentrations and excessive concentrations of ammonia and nitrite than ponds with low or moderate feeding rates (Tucker, Boyd, & McCoy, 1979). Poor water quality affects not only aquatic life but the surrounding ecosystem as well. Optimal water quality varies by species and needs to be monitored for optimal growth and survival of aquatic organisms including macro-invertebrates.

Pond is an aquatic fresh water micro-ecosystem & fairly a self sustainable unit in which all the four basic components of an ecosystem- Productivity, Decomposition, Energy flow & Nutrient cycling are well exhibited, with plant and animal life directly interacting and in equilibrium with the immediate environment. Pond ecosystem is blessed with their own importance in terms of biodiversity, ubiquity, abundance and source of hydration. In addition to the above virtues they also serve as the aesthetical values to the lives and nature. It is only relatively recently, that ponds have been widely recognized as an important freshwater habitats supporting aquatic biodiversity (Davies, Biggs, Williams, Whitfield, Nicolet, Sear, Bray, & Maund, 2008; Picazo, Bilton, Moreno, Sanchez-Fernandez, & Millan, 2012; Hassall & Anderson, 2015). Ponds are important hotspots of biodiversity and support a wide range of flora and fauna with highly variable life histories and habitat preferences. Ponds collectively support more species, and more scarce species, than any other fresh water habitat (Careghino, Biggs, Oertli, & Declerck, 2008). They are globally recognized as being particularly important for macroinvertebrate (Collinson, Biggs, Corfield, Hodson, Walker, Whitfield, & Williams, 1995 ; Oertli, Joye, Castella, Juge, Cambin, & Lachavanne, 2002; Nicolet, Biggs, Fox, Hodson, Reynolds, Withfield, & Williams, 2004). They are more abundant than almost any other fresh water habitat, and are found in virtually all environments. Despite this very little research has been conducted on ponds and their ecological values.

The macro in macro-invertebrates generally refers to invertebrates that are large enough to be seen with the unaided eye (Voshell & Reese, 2002) or to be retained by a standard sieve mesh opening size, usually about 500 microns (Mc Cafferty & Provonsha, 1981). Macroinvertebrates are ubiquitous, lack a backbone and are grouped into feeding groups of shredders, collectors, scrapers, and predators. Shredders feed on organic material, such as leaves and woody material, and help to convert this matter into finer particles. Collectors/Filterers feed on fine organic particles that have been produced by shredders, microorganisms and by physical processes. Scrapers/Grazers graze algae and other organic matter that is attached to rocks and plants. Predators feed on live prey and are found where smaller collectors and shredders exist. They may be categorized as Pollution sensitive, moderately pollution sensitive and Pollution tolerant. Pollution sensitive organisms require good water quality to survive. They may require high dissolved oxygen levels, or they may be predators that require an ample source of prey. The taxonomic orders of macro-invertebrates such as Ephemeroptera (E), Plecoptera (P), and Trichoptera (T) are in general three "Pollution sensitive" orders (Merritt & Cummins, 1996). Moderately pollution sensitive organisms require fair water quality to survive. Their habitat requirements aren't as stringent as pollution-sensitive organisms. Pollution tolerant organisms can survive in poor water quality. They often have adaptations that allow them to survive in water with low dissolved oxygen or nutrient-enriched waters. The taxonomic orders of macro-invertebrates such as Diptera, Gastropoda, Amphipoda, and Oligochaeta are in general "Pollution tolerant" orders. Sensitivity to environmental changes thus makes them good indicators of water condition. Feeding measures, such as % grazer or % filterer, reflect the sensitivity to available food resources (Resh, 1993). Macro-invertebrate are an integral link in the stream food chain (Allan 1995; Merritt & Cummins 1996). They are also important in the nutrient cycles, decomposition and in the transportation of some minerals.

The aquatic organisms have provided water quality assessment programmes with valuable insight for more than 100 years (Cairns & Pratt, 1993). Macro-invertebrates live in selected areas within water bodies depending on the physical, chemical and biological characteristics (Mason 2002; Wang & Lyons, 2003). Due to this fact macro-invertebrates have been used to predict water quality status of different water systems (Masese, Muchiri, & Raburu, 2009; Aura, Raburu, & Hermann, 2010). According to Carlisle, Meador, Moulton, & Ruhl, 2007, macro-invertebrate population in ponds, streams and rivers can assist in the assessment of the overall health of the water ecosystem as they utilize the organic and detritus matter. They also show the impacts from habitat loss not detected by traditional water quality assessments and are relatively easy to sample and identify. The understanding of the factors influencing the presence and relative abundance of macro-invertebrate trait over space and time can prove insight into the functional diversity of the community (Resh, Norrish, & Barbour, 1995; Beche & Resh, 2007, Sanchez – Montoya, Puntí, Suarez, Vidal- Abarca, Rieradevall, Poquet, Zamora-Munoz, Robles, Alvarez, Alba-Tercedor, Toro, Pujante, Munne, & Prat, 2007). The study of Physico-chemical parameters of any ecosystem could be used to analyze the production potential because several physical and chemical factors of water and soil can influence on productivity, abundance and species composition of all aquatic biota (Singh, Ramteke, Mishra, & Shukla, 2013). The life in aquatic environment is also governed by the Physico-chemical characteristic of the water body and its stability. Physico-chemical Parameters of water is important to know the quality of water before it is used for drinking, domestic, agricultural or industrial or any other

purpose. Water must be tested keeping in view of different Physico-chemical parameters. The selection of the parameters for testing of water quality depends totally upon the purpose we going to use that water and to what extent its quality and purity is needed. Physical and chemical analytical methods are used for testing of its Physico-chemical parameters such as water temperature, pH, DO, transparency, TDS, BOD, COD, alkalinity, free CO₂ and other such characters. Biodiversity surveys of aquatic macro-invertebrates and ecological studies in relation to Physico-chemical characteristics of pond water have been conducted on several Caribbean Islands and few researchers **Kiran, 2010; Raut, Shinde, Pathan, & Sonawane, 2011; Naik, Ajayan, & Lokesh, 2012; Bahekar & There, 2013; Mahajan & Tank, 2013**, in different regions of India. There is no information available in relation to the Physico-chemical characteristics of pond water at Aurangabad, Bihar, India. Hence the present investigation was undertaken with the following objectives in aquatic fresh water ponds of Aurangabad, Bihar, during the period of one year from Dec 2015 to Nov 2016.

1. To analyze and compare the Physico-chemical parameters of surface water and sediments in all the three selected fresh water ponds. The observations and analysis of pond water were made every month and that of pond water bottom sediment every 6 months for a period of one year from Dec 2015 to Nov 2016.
2. To determine the relative abundance and richness of aquatic macro-invertebrates species inhabiting the selected ponds.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A. Study Area, Sampling of pond water & Samplings of macro-invertebrate Biota

Aurangabad district, having three perennial ponds locally known as Pond I (Umga), Pond II (Ranipokharadeo) & Pond III (Patalganga).

The surface water samples were collected in clean plastic cans, once in a month from three different ponds. Later the data was pooled together and represented as monthly data of the pond. Water temperature was recorded on the spot. The samples for dissolved oxygen were fixed immediately on the field itself.

Samplings of Macro-invertebrate fauna were done following the methods described by **Welch, 1948**

B. Physicochemical parameters analysis:

The analysis of Physico-chemical parameters of the pond water were performed monthly using the standard methods of **Welch, 1948; APHA, 1981; NEERI, 1986**, that included Temperature, pH, TA (Total alkalinity), Free CO₂, DO (Dissolved Oxygen), EC (Electrical Conductivity), Transparency and BOD (Biological Oxygen Demand). Temperature of water was determined by thermometry method using a simple mercury thermometer. The pH was determined by electrometry method using pH meter systronics at room temperature (25°C). TA in terms of concentration of carbonate (CO₃²⁻) and bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) ions was estimated by titration

method with acid using phenolphthalein and methyl orange as indicators. Free CO₂ was estimated titrimetrically using phenolphthalein as indicator. The DO was estimated titrimetrically by winklers Iodometric method/use of an oxygen meter. The EC was estimated by electrometry method using a Systronics conductivity meter at room temperature (25°C). Transparency was estimated with a Secchi disk. BOD was estimated by incubation of a sample for 5 days at 20°C and adopting winklers Iodometric method.

The analysis of Physico-chemical parameters of the ponds bottom soil was also performed half yearly using standard methods that included pH, OC(Organic Carbon), N(Nitrogen), P(Phosphorus), and K(Potassium). The pH of soil was estimated by pH meter, OC by Walkely and Black tritration method, N by Kjeldahl's method, P by Volumetric method and K by Flame photometric method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The monthly value of different Physico-chemical parameters of water samples of three fresh water ponds is presented in **Table: 1 to 3**. The mean value analysis of the two readings of soil parameters of three fresh water ponds is presented in **Table: 4**. The Relative abundance of macro-invertebrate species recorded from all the three ponds are presented in **Table: 5**

Of the 33 taxa of macro-invertebrate fauna identified in selected pond water during the study period, 19 species of aquatic insects represented by seven orders: Ephemeroptera, Odonata, Hemiptera, Coleoptera, Diptera, Plecoptera, Trichoptera,, 2 species of arachnids, 1 species of crustaceans, 5 species of aquatic annelids, 4 species of molluscs, 1 species of platyhelminthes, & 1 species of aschelminthes were witnessed. The insect orders Ephemeroptera, Odonata, Hemiptera, Coleoptera (Beetles), Diptera (True flies), Plecoptera, and Trichoptera were represented by 2,2,2,5,5,2,1 species respectively. The most abundant taxa were *Limnodrilus* sp of annelids, *Chironomus*, *Procladius*, and *Goeldochironomus* sp of Diptera, Molluscan gastropoda (*Pila* sp.), Crustacean (*Hemigrapsus* sp), Hemiptera (*Corixa* sp of bugs), Odonata (*Sympetrum* sp of Dragon fly), Ephemeroptera (*Caenis* sp of mayfly), Trichoptera (*Lepidostoma* sp of caddis fly) and Coleoptera (*Berosus* sp.) There was spatial and temporal variation in abundance of different taxa collected. Some macro invertebrate assemblages changed seasonally because taxa have been found to colonize at different times of the year (**De Szalay & Resh, 2000**). Different taxonomic groups of macro invertebrates are sensitive to different pollutants and can act as key indicators of disturbance caused by stressor gradients (e.g., nutrient gradients) in pond ecosystems. These attributes of macro invertebrates make them attractive biological indicators in biological assessment programs and hence acts as key indicators of water quality conditions. Pollution-tolerant macro-invertebrate taxa is found to be more abundant at the freshwater nutrient-rich sites than at the oligotrophic reference sites (**Gray, 2005**). In particular, tolerant species of macro-invertebrates such as flatworms, gastropods, Hemipterans (*Corixa* sp of bugs) and chironomus sp of dipteran were usually abundant at the nutrient-rich sites, whereas pollution sensitive species such as Ephemeroptera (*Caenis* sp of

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mayfly), Trichoptera (*Lepidostoma* sp of caddis fly) were in far greater numbers at oligotrophic sites. The relative abundance of the taxa was found to be flourishing, showing that the good quality of pond water has appropriate Physico-parameters that favored a positive impact on the growth and survival of macro-invertebrate including the sensitive species.

Table 1: Monthly Physico- chemical analysis of Pond I (Umga)

Month	Air temp (°C)	Water temp. (°C)	pH	DO (mg/L)	Free CO ₂ (mg/L)	Total Alkalinity (mg/L)	Conductivity (µmhoscm ⁻¹)	Transparency (cm)	BOD (mg/L)
Dec 15	21.0	20.0	7.6	5.8	28	235	885	29	13.05
Jan 16	23.5	23.5	7.6	6.0	29	217	1042	28	13.10
Feb 16	23.0	23.0	7.5	5.8	26	205	1235	27	13.90
Mar 16	23.5	24.0	7.4	6.1	24	210	1258	25	13.55
Apr 16	27.0	25.5	7.3	6.6	22	214	1252	24	14.65
May16	29.0	29.5	7.5	7.6	18	229	1223	22	15.40
Jun 16	30.0	30.0	7.6	6.5	14	219	1170	23	15.25
Jul 16	32.5	30.5	7.5	6.5	22	225	996	24	15.00
Aug16	32.0	29.5	7.4	5.9	24	235	855	26	15.15
Sep 16	28.5	28.0	7.6	5.5	27	247	914	27	15.80
Oct 16	26.0	27.0	7.5	5.8	30	255	853	26	15.05
Nov16	23.5	24.5	7.5	6.2	31	237	835	28	14.75

Table 2: Monthly Physico-chemical analysis of Pond II (Ranipokharadeo)

Month	Air temp (°C)	Water temp. (°C)	pH	DO (mg/L)	Free CO ₂ (mg/L)	Total Alkalinity (mg/L)	Conductivity (µmhoscm ⁻¹)	Transparency (cm)	BOD (mg/L)
Dec 15	21.0	21.5	8.1	5.9	30	222	815	29	11.60
Jan 16	23.5	23.0	8.0	6.4	31	205	990	30	11.15
Feb 16	23.0	23.0	7.9	6.6	27	215	1100	29	11.90
Mar 16	23.5	24.5	7.8	6.9	22	222	1140	28	12.95
Apr 16	27.0	27.5	7.7	7.1	18	245	1152	26	13.25
May16	29.0	28.5	7.8	7.6	17	233	1022	24	13.15
Jun 16	30.0	30.5	7.8	7.8	20	229	1170	22	13.90
Jul 16	32.5	31.5	7.9	7.1	23	215	957	24	13.35
Aug16	32.0	31.0	8.0	6.9	24	205	899	25	12.95
Sep 16	28.5	29.5	8.1	6.3	26	198	984	27	12.80
Oct 16	26.0	25.5	7.9	5.9	28	225	874	29	12.75
Nov16	23.5	23.0	8.0	5.1	29	242	865	30	12.90

Table 3: Monthly Physico- chemical analysis of Pond III (Patalganga)

Month	Air temp (°C)	Water temp. (°C)	pH	DO (mg/L)	Free CO ₂ (mg/L)	Total Alkalinity (mg/L)	Conductivity (µmhos.cm ⁻¹)	Transparency (cm)	BOD (mg/L)
Dec 15	21.0	21.0	7.7	5.9	32	230	815	32	10.95
Jan 16	23.5	24.5	7.8	6.4	30	228	853	30	11.40
Feb 16	23.0	25.0	8.0	6.2	26	215	975	30	11.25
Mar 16	23.5	25.0	7.9	7.0	22	228	1030	27	12.55
Apr 16	27.0	25.5	7.8	7.2	19	206	1057	25	12.60
May16	29.0	28.5	7.7	7.6	15	218	1032	24	12.95
Jun 16	30.0	28.0	7.6	7.8	22	235	1105	23	12.80
Jul 16	32.5	30.5	7.6	7.7	24	225	972	25	12.65
Aug16	32.0	31.0	7.6	7.1	26	205	905	27	12.85
Sep 16	28.5	27.0	7.6	6.5	27	218	978	27	12.05
Oct 16	26.0	25.0	7.5	6.3	27	225	953	30	11.75
Nov16	23.5	24.0	7.5	6.6	28	215	904	31	11.50

Table 4: Soil analysis mean value data of the three ponds

Ponds	pH	OC (%)	N (mg Kg ⁻¹)	P (mg Kg ⁻¹)	K (mgKg ⁻¹)
Pond I (Umga)	7.3	3.90	205	12.15	38.55
Pond II (Ranipokharadeo)	7.6	2.45	195	9.35	31.25
Pond III (Patalganga)	7.8	3.75	285	12.80	55.40

Table 5: Relative abundance of macro-invertebrate species recorded from three ponds.

Sl.No	Macro-invertebrate species recorded from pond (Taxa)	Relative abundance		
		Pond I	Pond II	Pond III
Platyhelminthes: Turbellaria				
	<i>Rhabdoceola</i> sp.	+	-	-
Aschelminthes : Nematoda				
	<i>Dorylaimida</i> sp.	+	-	-
Annelida: Oligochaetes				
	<i>Tubifex</i> sp.	+	-	+
	<i>Limnodrilus</i> sp.	+	+	++
	<i>Dero</i> sp	-	-	+
	<i>Eiseniella</i> sp.	++	-	-
	<i>Chaetogaster</i> sp.	+	-	+

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Arthropoda				
1. Insecta.				
(a)	Ephemeroptera			
	<i>Caenis</i>	-	-	+
	<i>Habrophlebiodes</i> sp	+	+	+
(b)	Odonata-			
	<i>Sympetrum</i> sp.	+	+	+
	<i>Lestes</i> sp.	++	-	+
(c)	Hemiptera			
	<i>Corixa punctata</i>	+	-	-
	<i>Gerris</i> sp.	+	+	++
(d)	Coleoptera			
	<i>Berosus</i> sp.	++	-	++
	<i>Tropisternus</i> sp	++	+	+
	<i>Gyrinus</i> sp.	+	-	+
	<i>Laccodytes</i> sp.	+	+	+
	<i>Hydrophilus</i> sp.	+	-	+
(e)	Diptera			
	<i>Culex</i> sp.	+	-	++
	<i>Procladius</i> sp.	++	-	+
	<i>Chironomus</i> sp.	++	+	+
	<i>Tabanus</i> sp	++	-	+
	<i>Goeldochironomus</i> sp.	++	+	+
(f)	Plecoptera			
	<i>Phanoperla</i>	+	-	-
	<i>Indonemoura</i>	-	-	+
(g)	Trichoptera			
	<i>Lepidostoma</i>	++	-	+
2. Hydracarina (Arachnids)				
	<i>Eylais tantilla</i> (Koen)	+	-	-
	<i>Hydracna skorikowi</i> (Piersig)	-	-	+
3. Crustacea				
	<i>Hemigrapsus</i> sp.	+	-	-
Mollusca				
	<i>Physa</i> sp.	+	-	-
	<i>Gyraulus</i> sp.	-	-	-
	<i>Lymnae</i> sp.	+	-	+
	<i>Pila globosa</i> .	+	+	+

Conclusion:

The Physico-chemical parameters of three pond water was found to be in the range of water temperature 20.0- 31.5°C, pH 7.3-8.1, DO 5.1– 7.8 mg/L, free carbon dioxide 14- 32 mg/L, TA 198-255 mg/L, EC 815 – 1258 $\mu\text{mhos cm}^{-1}$, Transparency 22- 31 cm and BOD 10.95.00- 15.80 mg/L. The nutritional status of the three pond bottom soil was found to be in range of pH 7.3 - 7.8, OC 2.45 - 3.90 %, N 195 - 285 mg Kg^{-1} , P 9.35 - 12.80 mg Kg^{-1} and K 31.25 - 55.40 mg Kg^{-1} . The analyzed Physico-chemical parameters of pond water and soil samples under study were found to be around or within range of the permissible limits that favoured the pond production potential in terms of productivity, abundance and species composition of aquatic macro-invertebrate. Thus the permissible parameters provided a good Impact on macro-invertebrate survival, growth, abundance and composition.

REFERENCES:

Allan, D. (1995). Stream Ecology: Structure and function of running waters, Chapman and Hall.

APHA, (1981). American Public Health Association, Standard methods for examination of water and waste water, Washington USA.

Aura, C.M., Raburu, P.O., Hermann, J. (2010). Preliminary macroinvertebrate IBI for biossesment of the kipkaren and the soslani Rivers, Nzoia River Basin, Kenya. Lakes and Reservoirs 15(2): [pp 119-128]

Bahekar, R., There, Y. (2013). Seasonal variation in physico-chemical characteristics of Koradi Lake, district Nagpur, India. Indian Streams Research Journal, 3(2): [pp 1-5]

Beche, L.A. & Resh, V.H. (2007). Short- term climatic trends affect the temporal variability Of macro-invertebrates in California Mediterranean streams. Fresh water Biol. 52:[pp 2317-2339].

Boyd, C. E. and Tucker, C.S. (1998). Pond Aquaculture Water Quality Management. Kluwer Academic Publishers, Boston, Massachusetts.

Cairns, J. and Pratt, J.R. (1993). A history of biological monitoring using benthicmacro-invertebrates. [pp 10-27] In: Fresh water Biomonitoring and Benthic Macro-invertebrates. Chapman and Hall, New York, 1993

Careghino, R., Biggs, J., Oertli, B., and Declerck, S. (2008). The ecology of European ponds: Defining the characteristics of a neglected fresh water habitat. Hydrobiologia 597: [pp 1-6]

Carlisle, D.M.; Meador, M.R.; Moulton, S.R.; Ruhl, P.M. (2007). Estimation and applications of indicator values for common macro-invertebrate. Ecol. Indicators, 7; [pp 22-33]

Collinson, N.H., Biggs, J., Corfield, A., Hodson, M.J., Walker, D., Whitfield, M., Williams, P.J. (1995). Temporary and permanent ponds: an assessment of the effects of drying out on the conservation value of aquatic macroinvertebrate communities. *Biol. Conserv.*, 74, [pp. 125-133]

Davies, B.R., Biggs, J., Williams, P., Whitfield, M., Nicolet, P., Sear, D., Bray, S., Maund, S. (2008). Comparative biodiversity of aquatic habitats in the European agricultural landscape. *Agricultural, Ecosystems & Environment*, 125, [pp 1-8]

De Szalay, F. A. and Resh, V. H. (2000). Factors influencing macroinvertebrate colonization of seasonal wetlands: responses to emergent plant cover. *Freshwater Biology*, 45, 295-308.

Diersing and Nancy (2009). "Water Quality: Frequently asked questions." FLORIDA BROOKS NATIONAL MARINE SANCTUARY, KEY WEST, FL.

Dudgeon, D. (2006). Freshwater biodiversity: Importance, threats, status and conservation challenges. *Biological Reviews* 81, [pp 163-182]

Ghose, B.B. and Basu, A. K. (1968). Observation on Estuarine Pollution of the Hooghly by the Effluents from a Chemical Factory Complex at Reshasa, West Bengal. *Environmental Health*, 10, [pp 209-218].

Gray, L. J. (2005). Composition of Macroinvertebrate Communities of the Great Salt Lake Wetlands and Relationships to Water Chemistry. Prepared for Utah Department of Environmental Quality, Division of Water Quality (UDWQ). March.

Gupta, S. and Shukla, D. N. (2006). Physico-Chemical Analysis of Sewage Water and its Effect on Seed Germination and Seedling Growth of *Sesamum indicum*. *Journal of Research in National Development*, 1, [pp 15-19]

Hassal & Anderson (2015). Storm water ponds can contain comparable biodiversity to unmanaged wetlands in urban areas, *Hydrobiologia*, 745, [pp 137-149.]

Johnson, D.L., Ambrose, S.H. Ambrose, Bassett, T.J., Bowen, M.L., Crummey, D.E., Isaacson, J.S., Johnson, D.N., Lamb, P., Saul, M., AND Winter-Nelson, A.E., (1997). Meanings of environmental terms. *Journal of Environmental quality*.26: [pp 581-589]

Kataria, H.C., Gupta, M.K., Kushwaha, S., Kashyap, S., Trivedi, S., Bhadoriya, R., Bandewar, N.K. (2011). Study of physico-chemical parameters of drinking water of Bhopal city with Reference to Health Impacts. *Current World Environment*, 6(1): [pp 95-99]

Kiran, B.R. (2010). Physico-chemical characteristics of Fish Ponds of Bhadra project at Karnataka, India. *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*, 3(4): [pp 671-676]

Mahajan, A., Tank, S.K. (2013). Studies on the physico-chemical parameters of water body-Dara Dam, Maharashtra, India. International Journal of Innovative Research and Development, 2(3): [pp 751-759]

Manjare, S.A., Vhanalakar, S.A., Muley, D.V. (2010). Analysis of water quality using physico-chemical parameters tamdalge tank in kolhapurdistrict, Maharashtra. International Journal of Advanced Biotechnology and Research,1(2): [pp 115-119]

Masese, F.O., Muchiri, M., Raburu, P.O. (2009). Macroinvertebrate assemblages as biological indicators of water quality in the Moiben River, Kenya, Afr.J.Aqua.Sc.34:[pp 15-26].

Mason, C.F. (2002). Biology of fresh water pollution. 4th edition. Pearson education Ltd. Essex London. 38 pp.

McCafferty, W. P., and Provonsha, A., (1981). Aquatic entomology: the fishermens and ecologists illustrated guide to insects and their relatives. Science Books International, Boston, M.A.

Merritt, R. W., and Cummins, K. W. (1996). An introduction to the aquatic insects of North America, Kendallll Hunt Publishing, Dubuque, Iowa.

Naik, T.P., Ajayan, K.V., Lokesh, G.H. (2012). Physico-chemical characteristics of Kunigal Lake in Tumkur district, Karnataka, India. International Journal Chemical Science, 10(2): [pp 655-663]

NEERI, (1986). Manual of water and waste water analysis. National Environmental Engineering Research Institute, Nehru marg, Nagpur.

Nicolet, P., Biggs, J., Fox, G., Hodson, M.J., Reynolds, C., Withfield, M., Williams, P. (2004). The wetland plant and macroinvertebrate assemblages of temporary ponds in England and Wales. Biol. Conserv., 120 , [pp. 265-282]

Oertli, B., Joye, D.A., Castella, E., Juge, R., Cambin, D., Lachavanne, J.B. (2002). Does size matter? The relationship between pond area and biodiversity. Biol. Conserv., 104 , [pp. 59-70]

Patil, D. B. and Tijare, R. V. (2001). Studies on Water Quality of Godchiroli Lake. Pollution Research, 20: [pp 257-259]

Picazo, F., Bilton, D.T., Moreno, J.L., Sanchez-Fernandez, D., Millan, A. (2012). Water beetle biodiversity in Mediterranean standing waters: assemblage composition, environmental drivers & nestedness patterns. Insect conservation & Diversity, 5, [pp 146-158]

Raut, K.S., Shinde, S.E., Pathan, T.S., Sonawane, D.L. (2011). Seasonal variations in physico-chemical characteristics of Peth Lake at Ambajogai district, BeedMarathwada Region, India. *Journal of Research in Biology*, 1(4): [pp 258-262]

Resh, V., (1993). Freshwater biomonitoring and benthic macroinvertebrates. Chapman and Hall. New York, NY. And London. [Pp 1-473]

Resh, V., Norrish R.H., Barbour, M.T. (1995). Design and implementation of rapid assessment approaches for water resource monitoring using benthic macro-invertebrates. *Aust J Ecol.* 20: [pp 198-219.]

Sala, O. E (2000). Biodiversity- Global biodiversity scenarios for the year 2100. *Science* 287, [pp 1770-1774]

Sanchez – Montoya M, Punti T., Suarez M.L., Vidal- Abarca, M., Rieradevall M., Poquet J.M., Zamora-Munoz C., Robles S., Alvarez M., Alba-Tercedor J., Toro M., Pujante A.M., Munne A., Prat N. (2007). Concordance between ecotypes and macro-invertebrate assemblages in Mediterranean streams. *Fresh water Biol.* 52: [pp 2240-2255]

Shrivastava, S., Kanungo, V.K. (2013). Physico-Chemical Analysis of Pond Water of Surguja District, Chhattishgarh, India. *International Journal of Herbal Medicine*, 1(4): [pp 35-43]

Singh, R.K., Ramteke, P.W., Mishra, S and Shukla, P.K. (2013). Physico-chemical analysis of Yamuna River Water. *International Journal of Research in Environmental Science and Technology*, 3(2), [pp 58-60.]

Singh, R.P. and Mathur, P. (2005). Investigation of Variation in Physico-Chemical Characteristics of a Fresh Water Reservoir of Ajmer city, Raj. *Indian Journal of Environmental Science*, 9, [pp 57-61].

Tucker, L. S., Boyd, C.E., and McCoy, E.W. (1979). Effects of feeding rate on water quality, production of channel catfish, and economic returns. *Transactions of the American Fisheries Society* 108: [pp 389-396].

Voshell, J. & Reese, J. (2002). A Guide to Common Freshwater Invertebrates of North America. The McDonald & Woodward Publishing Company, Blacksburg, Virginia.

Wang, L., and Lyons, J. (2003). Fish and benthic macro-invertebrate assemblage as indicators of stream degradation in urbanizing watersheds. In *Biological Response Signatures: Indicator Patterns Using Aquatic Communities* (Simon, T.P., ed), CRC Press Boca Raton, [pp 113-120]

Welch, P.S. (1948). Limnological methods, Mc Graw Hill Book Co. INC. New York